

paper Chain

Guidelines for the implementation of the
Circular Economy models.

FACTSHEET CC3

**Transport infrastructure sector- railways.
MUDIPEL®.**

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New Market Niches For the Pulp and Paper Industry Waste based on Circular Economy Approaches

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Keywords

Guidelines	Construction material	Pulp & Paper Industry (PPI)	Circular Economy Model (CEM)	Fact sheet
assessment	requirement	standard	Waste	performance
Back-fill material	Deinking paper ash (DPA)	Deinking paper sludge (DPS)	Gabion	railways

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Circular Model Guidelines CC3: Transport infrastructure sector-railways. MUDIPEL®.

CC3: Deinking ash and sludge use in MUDIPEL® back-fill material production:

This Circular Model CC3 is focused on the use of an innovative composite MUDIPEL®, based on PPI wastes use as light backfill alternative material in successful gabions construction at railways landslides restoration in Slovenia. The composite is a mix of 70 % of deinking paper ash (DPA) and 30 % of deinking paper sludge (DPS). After compaction can develop a considerable strength (>1 MPa at 28 curing days) and low permeability, achieving optimal properties for the intended use. VIPAP (PPI industry) collaborates with Dušan Holešek (construction SME) and ZAG (Research institute and notifying body granted the Slovenian Technical Approval (STS), and SZ Infrastructure (Railways infrastructure operator, end User). TECNALIA supported in the environmental performance monitoring design and validation. Performance achieved user requirements, but process has some critical points: proper wastes mixing, humidity control and compaction and environmental monitoring. CC3 has a high replicability potential. This light material could be employed in roads, mining restoration. STS approval grants the use of MUDIPEL® in Slovenia. Figure 1 shows the CC3 Circular Case in Slovenia. Construction of MUDIPEL based construction designs for railways slopes stabilization, Figures 2 to 4 show the industrial scale pilot demonstration, and Tables 1 and 2 CC main items, key factors and lessons learnt.

CC3 LANDSLIDE STABILIZATION BACKFILL MATERIAL WITH DPA/DPS WASTES, SHORT GUIDELINES:

- ✦ Circular Economy Models using DPA/DPS wastes based new material (MUDIPEL®) as back-fill material is developed in PAPERCHAIN. Lack of specific EU regulation and standards for its use as back-fill material impedes a wider market penetration, despite MUDIPEL® showing an optimal technical and environmental performance. Challenges: material handling, homogeneous mixing and compaction requiring new skills and adapted equipment, but affordable considering existing industrial equipment. Replicability still limited to Slovenia.

FIGURE 1 – C3 CIRCULAR CASE (SLOVENIA). LANDSLIDES STABILISATION WITH MUDIPEL.

FIGURE 2 – WASTE. DPA + DPS = MUDIPEL®. BACK-FILL LIGHT MATERIAL.

FIGURE 3 – PROCESS. RETAINING WALL CONSTRUCTION WITH MUDIPEL®.

Before:

After:

FIGURE 4 – APPLICATION. RETAINING WALL WITH MUDIPEL®.

TABLE 1 PAPERCHAIN CIRCULAR CASE 3 LANDSLIDE STABILIZATION, MAIN ITEMS

<i>item</i>	<i>Description</i>
PAPERCHAIN STAKEHOLDERS	VIPAP (DPA/DPS wastes producer PPI) , Dušan Holešek (Construction SME); SZ infrastructure (Railway manager); ZAG (Research institute); TECNALIA (Research Centre).
LOCATION	South Slovenia, between Ljubljana and Novo Mesto.
WASTE	Deinking Paper Ash (DPA) + Deinking Paper Sludge (DPS)
PRODUCT	MUDIPEL®
APPLICATION	Back fill material for slope stabilization for retaining walls (gabions) in near railways.

TABLE 2 CC3 MUDIPEL BASED GABIONS. KEY FACTORS AND LESSONS LEARNT

<i>Key Factor</i>	<i>Fact</i>	<i>Lessons learnt</i>
Waste (DPA+DPS)	<p>Deinking Paper Ash (DPA)</p> <p>Deinking Paper Sludge (DPS)</p> <p>Non-hazardous wastes of similar chemical and mineralogical compositions.</p>	<p>MUDIPEL (70% DPA + 30% DPS) meets all technical requirements from STS (Slovenian Technical Approval).</p> <p>Do not experience critical volumetric changes, is an impermeable material. Technical and environmental suitable.</p>
Regulatory framework	<p>Lack of specific regulation and EU standards about the use of DPS and PSA in gabion constructions.</p> <p>Sharp environmental constrains in some Ms (such as Slovenia) for use of these wastes.</p>	<p>Lack of specific regulation about DPS and DPA individual use as back-fill material in construction (gabions, retaining walls, etc.), or as a mix, as MUDIPEL®, can be overcome by Slovenian Technical Approval (STS - Slovenian Technical Approval procedure) for Slovenian market, and for EU market through EAD doc. In any case, getting</p>

	<p>STS - Slovenian Technical Approval procedure for MUDIPEL® granted.</p> <p>EAD in preparation</p>	<p>approvals supposes a big resources and time consuming process.</p>
<p>Proceedings</p>	<p>Challenges: procuring regular availability and “homogeneous” quality SRM for MUDIPEL® production.</p> <p>Mixing, homogenization and compaction are critical.</p> <p>The material can be installed in at least 30cm thick layers.</p>	<p>Constrains on optimal workability time after mixing (<4h).</p> <p>Compaction at works site may need more effort than usual materials.</p> <p>MUDIPEL® characteristics enables constructor building less gabions construction per same length.</p> <p>New skills, and new mixing equipment are needed. Continuous control during the production, mixing and installation stages of MUDIPEL is necessary in order to get high quality back-fill material.</p>
<p>Barriers</p>	<p>Lack of specific regulation and EU standards about the use of DPS and PSA in railways gabion constructions.</p> <p>Lack of many experiences on MUDIPEL® based end-product long-term technical and environmental performance. Yet some lack of confidence from the construction sector.</p>	<p>EU specific regulation and standards about the use of DPA and DSA is necessary to boost the use of such materials.</p> <p>Technical and environmental performance very long term (several years of functioning) to be demonstrated and disseminated yet.</p>
<p>Enablers</p>	<p>DPA and DPS waste landfilling not possible in Slovenia, but abroad (Austria). Elevated landfilling costs (80-150€/ton). Main enabler.</p> <p>The use of MUDIPEL improves the stability of the slope, not supposing a negative impact for the environment.</p> <p>Impermeability confirmed with the monitoring system installed in the retaining wall.</p>	<p>MUDIPEL® offers a good technical and environmental performance according to the period of pilot observation (2 year). Longer period performance to be demonstrated.</p> <p>Potential use in other applications in the construction sector (roads, mining) are promising. This can boost the use of MUDIPEL®.</p>

	<p>MUDIPEL is a light-weight material with really high shear strength parameters.</p>	
<p>LCA/CO2 footprint</p>	<p>MUDIPEL® supposes an increase of the circularity index of construction of gabions, as alternative to standard natural raw materials, while a reduction of the CO₂ footprint.</p>	<p>Carbon footprint reduction is limited by its transportation from MUDIPEL production facility to the construction site.</p> <p>Recyclability of constructed material can be granted if correct dismantling is applied.</p>
<p>Exploitation</p>	<p>MUDIPEL® as new light back-fill material.</p> <p>Exploitation will be possible in Slovenia as STS technical approval is granted. For the rest of EU market still not possible. Unique potential location for MUDIPEL® production (VIPAP) at the moment.</p> <p>-High DPA and DPS landfilling constrains and costs are the main factor for pushing for a DPA and DPS valorization.</p> <p>Additional effort on compaction at works and long-term monitoring may increase the overall construction costs.</p>	<p>MUDIPEL® production can be reproduced in other EU similar facilities.</p> <p>Lack of specific regulation and standard about DPA / DPS use as back-fill material impedes a faster market penetration.</p> <p>Each Ms has a very different technical regulation and requirements regarding to railway and slopes stability and environmental requirements that may impede a homogeneous market penetration.</p> <p>Construction is a very conservative sector but novel constructions with lighter materials as MUDIPEL® in roads and mining reclamation are to be explored.</p>
<p>Replicability potential</p>	<p>MUDIPEL® has a big potential as a back-fill material in railway slope stabilization, but also, as alternative light and impermeable material in other construction applications (roads, mining and polluted soils reclamation).</p>	<p>CC3 CEM can be reproduced in other EU Ms PPI similar facilities.</p>